

eLTER Preparatory Phase Project

Roadmap for European and global partnerships

Deliverable D1.3

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1 Introduction

The first version of the eLTER vision and mission, which was adopted by the eLTER Interim Council in June 2021, is technically the eLTER PPP deliverable D1.1 (Nikolaidis et al 2021). Four main strategic goals were identified to accomplish the vision and mission of eLTER. These strategic goals are:

1. Facilitate innovative research for addressing grand societal challenges
2. Design and operate a distributed and highly functional network of eLTER in-situ facilities across Europe
3. Create a unique and widely accessible service portfolio
4. Promote collaboration, integration, and a conducive working culture

To achieve these strategic goals, specifically goal 4, the eLTER RI will build on sustainable strategic partnerships. The purpose of these partnerships are synergies and to promote and enable a wider range of strategic, scientific, technological and operational collaborations. Co-location of in-situ facilities with existing and emerging environmental monitoring networks and research infrastructures and initiatives shall be achieved where reasonable. In line with the current EC strategic priorities, this endeavour will consider both the European and international context to maximize the uptake of its services, strengthen its policy impact, avoid redundancy, and make productive use of complementary services provided by sister RIs. eLTER is well positioned to do this with our long history in being leadingly involved in the International Long-Term Ecological Research network ILTER, in addition to the many European initiatives (see below).

In the context of eLTER's strategic planning, a stakeholder analysis was done (Barov et al 2021, D7.1), which identified "Peers in research & observation" identified as one of the seven priority stakeholder categories. Peers in environmental research and observation are related in-situ and remote monitoring and observation networks and organizations such as UNECE-Working Group on Effects, WMO, JRC and ESA/Copernicus or related research infrastructures in the environmental domain. Within this category, also European scale e-infrastructures (e.g. LifeWatch) and e-infrastructure initiatives like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) need to be taken into account as stakeholders interacting with the eLTER Data Architectures and data based services.

This report focuses particularly on the positioning and working relations of the emerging eLTER RI among the European and global environmental peer RIs and networks, which are of highest relevance for the design of eLTER RI, for the continental scale division of tasks and for the co-development of service components. Additionally, we present priorities for the further mid-term and long-term positioning in the European and global landscape.

2 Methodology

In order to support long-term consistency of eLTER strategy building and seamlessly capitalize on related previous activities, decisive input to the eLTER stakeholder analysis and engagement planning was drawn from past eLTER projects, such as eLTER H2020 project (H2020-funded project, GA: 654359), the eLTER ESFRI Roadmap proposal (2017), and the ENVRI PLUS project in collaboration with the other terrestrial environmental research infrastructures (Kutsch et al. 2017, D12.3). The European Research Infrastructures analysed

in Kutsch et al. were defined from the ESFRI Process and comprised the ESFRI Landmarks (ICOS ERIC, Lifewatch ERIC), and ESFRI Projects (eLTER and AnaEE) in the field of ecosystem and biodiversity research. They are mainly based on distributed in-situ networks of field stations (with the exception of LifeWatch ERIC which is an e-infrastructure).

The recent work during eLTER Preparatory Phase also intended to enhance awareness and to engage the entire consortia of eLTER PPP and eLTER PLUS in mapping **eLTER’s broader environment**. The eLTER consortia were consulted about relevant elements of this environment. This was done by the eLTER PLUS WP2 using a mindmapping approach, and partly in interactive participation of the community (e.g. in a dedicated session of the spring 2021 consortia meeting) to further specify the components in the mindmap and identify key responsibilities (‘key accounts’) in developing/maintaining the contacts (for details see eLTER PLUS deliverable D2.1). The mindmap of eLTER’s environment (Figure 1) reveals elements, which might not be primarily users, but are of high relevance for clarifying eLTER’s functional niche in the European RI landscape and are highly relevant for co-design and co-development of services.

Figure 1: Full view of the MindMap v26 of eLTER RI’s environment before synchronization with the stakeholder and user analysis.

In parallel, the mentioned **stakeholder analysis** was carried out **with a focus on existing and potential users of eLTER RI and its services**. The outcomes are primarily supposed to structure and target service development, training and communication (Barov et al 2021, eLTER PPP D7.1) to best possibly serve the users. The stakeholders were eventually categorized to 7 main categories with several stakeholder groups assigned to each of them. In Table 1 below those of highest relevance for this deliverable are highlighted in bold.

Table 1: eLTER Stakeholder categories (left) and assigned eLTER Stakeholder groups (right). Groups of highest relevance in the first phase of positioning and co-design/-development highlighted in bold.

Stakeholder category	Stakeholder group
Researchers and science stakeholders	
	Researchers, university students
	Research performing organisations (RPOs)
	Disciplinary research communities
	High level assessment and recommendation frameworks
	Pertinent initiatives and institutions
	Scientific councils
	Research networks
Research and Research Infrastructure funders	
	National funders
	European funders
	International funders
Peers in environmental research and observation	
	Monitoring and observation networks and organizations in-situ and remote
	Environmental Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)
	Global peers
Internal stakeholders	
	Site and platform coordinators
	Site and platform operating institutions
	National LTER networks coordination teams
Government and policy decision-makers	
	European policy makers
	European agencies
	National policy makers
	Regional and local authorities
	Global agencies and intergovernmental organisations
Business and industry	
	Natural resource users
	Secondary and service industries

	Sensor and instrument manufacturers
	ICT developers & service providers
	Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)
	Landscape and site planners and environmental consultants
Civil society and interested members of the public	
	Citizen science organisations
	Environmental NGOs
	Land and forest owners' organisations
	Associations promoting science and education

In a third step, the mindmap of the broader environment (incl. key eLTER components established to interact with the environment) was re-structured to achieve a maximum of compliance amongst the two angles. The following Figure 2 provides an overview of all components.

Figure 2: Overview of the synchronized MindMap of eLTER’s environment down to level 3.

Figure 3 zooms into the MindMap branches of highest relevance for this report.

Figure 3: Partial view of the elaborated and synchronized MindMap v30 of eLTER RI’s environment containing relevant peers in the European RI landscape and continental scale environmental monitoring, and priority global partnerships. The green elements at the outer edge are candidates from amongst the eLTER community, which will be established as key accounts responsible of the respective interfaces. In order to achieve complementarity further activities will distinguish between focal partners for the eLTER RI co-design and formalized collaboration (structure, services etc.: focus of eLTER PPP) and the comprehensive general networking (covered by the eLTER PLUS project).

3 Peers in environmental research and observation

3.1 The European peer relationships and fields of collaboration

Although there is a broad consensus about the many scientific, societal and economic benefits of close RI collaborations, such as e.g. exemplified in the ENVRI Cluster projects and the ENVRI Community (envri.eu), in praxis there is still a tendency to act in isolation or in parallel with similar or complimentary RIs (e.g., due to competitive overall settings in response to project calls). Thus any concrete RI-RI coordination and collaboration, or even integration, are poised to yield added value and significant synergies.

It is conceivable that the environmental RIs in Europe constitute a federated landscape, potentially representing a very large-scale pan-European facility, with different focus areas and methods but often shared facilities and many common stakeholders. A federated approach helps to reduce overlaps, to maximize synergies and benefits, and to coordinate Research Infrastructures in order to optimize observing systems ranging from in-situ and remote sensing data measurement and collection, to data analysis in the laboratory. Thus, clustering the environmental RIs is a natural consequence and has been greatly valued by the ESFRI (e.g. ESFRI 2018). The peer Research Infrastructures and networks in environmental research in Europe formed already early on an ENVRI cluster that has been closely collaborating for over a decade. The evolution of ENVRI community cooperation started from the publication of the first ESFRI roadmap in 2008, where the environmental domain was clearly identified and recognized to have many commonalities in their missions and operations, that warrant to be coordinated. It was obvious that environmental RIs would face similar challenges in their implementation, and that led to the onset of the cluster projects ENVRI (FP7, 2011-2014), ENVRIplus ('Environmental Research Infrastructures Providing Shared Solutions for Science and Society') H2020, 2015-2019) and the current ENVRI-FAIR (H2020, 2019-2022). These three projects, funded by the European Commission H2020 Framework Programme, have been working towards tools for a better integration of the European environmental RI landscape, and eLTER has been involved from the beginning.

The ENVRI cluster also strives for positioning the ENV RIs in the global playing field through its presence in GEO, various international fora, participating in projects to enhance global collaboration (COOP+, GLOBIS-B) and the AGU conference for instance. The ENVRI projects have aimed at improving the Earth observation monitoring systems and strategies, including actions to improve harmonization and innovation, and generating common solutions to many shared information technology and data related challenges. They also sought to harmonize policies for access and provide strategies for knowledge transfer amongst RIs. The consortium partners shared a common motivation derived from the global grand challenges (climate change, food security, environmental risks, sustainable use of natural resources, etc.) and from the UN SDGs, which each of the partners address with their specific methods and tools. The different terrestrial RIs clustered within ENVRI have a high potential of scientific cooperation, co-location and data interoperability. The ENVRI Reference Model v2.2 (published 30th October 2017) (www.envri.eu/rm) was created in the ENVRI, and ENVRIplus projects as a blueprint for developing synergies and promoting harmonized operations especially in data acquisition, curation and access. It represents a design framework for interoperability between infrastructures (Figure 4).

Figure 4: The ENVRI Reference Model. The ENVRI RM divides the modelling of RI systems across five viewpoints. This offers the mechanisms to map and keep the consistency of design across viewpoints, facilitating analysis, maintenance and evolution of systems.

In addition to collaboration in ongoing RI operations, ENVRI has also created a strategic forum, the Board of European Environmental Research infrastructures (BEERi), consisting of the coordinations of the RIs in the ENVRI community form. eLTER participates in the work of BEERi, which meets twice a year to discuss joint strategies and communication efforts of the environmental RIs. Examples are joint booths at EGU, GEO and AGU conferences, Hackathons, consortia building for Horizon EU calls, joint training and liaison with business and industry.

Another important achievement was the establishment of consensual graphical representations of the ENV RIs landscape reflecting the functional niches, formalization level and topical proximity of RIs (Figure 5, Figure 6).

Figure 5: ENVRIplus overview of environmental RIs divided by domains. eLTER’s whole system approach accounts for the position close to the central multi-domain RIs. Figure from the ENVRI Community.

Figure 6: ENVRIplus community landscape with a focus on the environmental domain and illustrating the close linkedness of domains. Figure from ENVRI community.

The emerging eLTER RI is fully embedded in the Biosphere and Ecosystems domain of ESFRI and has a long history of joint activities with many ENVRI Cluster members. The challenges, user needs and services provided to society by the environmental infrastructures in different

domains are very much interlinked and no one RI will be able to solve the Grand Challenges alone. It is also clear that RIs within a domain are able to complement each other and jointly provide tools and solutions for societies to tackle the challenges. In summer 2021, the ENVRI synergies and cross-disciplinary collaboration were utilized in creating a comprehensive proposal for the RI services for Climate risks (in the HorizonEurope first call 2021).

In addition to the cluster activities, we can identify several bilateral interactions of the research infrastructures in the domain that will help to optimise complementary services and synergies for integrated research projects (see below 3.3.1).

3.1.1 Design and data as forms of collaboration

Basically, a comprehensive cross-infrastructure documentation describing multiple use of sites was still missing for a long time. eLTER established a harmonized documentation of all in-situ observational sites and facilities in Europe and globally in a common registry and documentation system pilot, the Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and Dataset Registry (DEIMS-SDR, www.deims.org). Besides from a quantitative documentation of all LTER sites around the globe, several RIs and networks have already been described by a few fundamental DEIMS attributes, resulting in a broad availability of site metadata from a large number of co-located sites. DEIMS can be used e.g., in searching the best possible combination of sites for addressing a specific research question.

Being part of the ENVRI community has formed a good foundation for bi- and multilateral collaboration in many key activities. Among ENVRIs focused on terrestrial ecosystems and biodiversity, the potential for harmonization and coordination of activities among the RIs, such as development of core variables, data interoperability and co-location were outlined in the Kutsch et al. (2017, D12.3).

In this analysis, technical options for a comprehensive spatial analysis of sites across RIs were explored to detect clusters of sites, where the spatial proximity suggests existing or potential multiple use of (1) the same facilities or (2) facilities located so close to each other, that there might be a potential for combined/joined usage by more than one RI in investigating different aspects of a given ecosystem (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Workflow in exploring co-location potential amongst environmental RIs based on site metadata in DEIMS-SDR. From left to right: 1) Identifying hot spots based on spatial proximity, 2) exploring the composition of clusters (AnaEE, ICOS, eLTER) and 3) using standardized site metadata for a more detailed assessment of the potential and deriving recommendations.

The co-location (several RIs and networks operating at the same location) is a way to search for a higher impact and to avoid duplication of efforts, and eLTER is determined to test and screen the opportunities for this. Shared administration, harmonized observational schemes

and joint facilities and staff are increasing cost-efficiency and adding scientific value to the research done at the co-located sites.

In the broader European environmental research network landscape where, over decades, numerous projects, flagships and initiatives have been established, eLTER is working in close interaction, developing many types of common interfaces and services. The contributions and co-developing of services between eLTER and the other initiatives are realised in e.g. semantics (EnvThes, <http://vocabs.ceh.ac.uk/edg/tbl/EnvThes.editor>, EnvThes is hosted by UKRI-CEH using TopBraid and governed by LTER Europe), metadata and site description, data flows, standards and harmonisation, and user group involvement.

3.1.2 Organisational and political forms of collaboration

The European RI landscape is formally structured by national scale and European scale Roadmaps, which are outlining the strategic priorities of organizations, countries and the EU in supporting key RIs. The national and ESFRI roadmaps are often closely linked, so that an RI listed in the ESFRI Roadmap has a priority in the national roadmap over others. Roadmaps are a proven planning tool to seek in-country support from various sources and sectors of society. National roadmapping processes differ significantly between countries. In many countries, the position in a national roadmap is a prerequisite for being able to propose funding for developing and upgrading the national RIs, but very few countries recognize the concrete steps towards a better integration between RIs, which leads to disparate funding schemes and potential gaps in funding if the country is committed to many ESFRIs already. However, in some cases the national consortia have developed integrated concepts for an 'umbrella' RI that covers several ESFRI landmarks, projects and emerging projects.

As eLTER is listed in the ESFRI Roadmap since 2018, it is fundamental that eLTER aims at actively pursuing the inclusion of the national LTER networks and eLTER RI in all national roadmaps, and in this way opening the possibilities for receiving national support to the eLTER Sites and Platforms. In eLTER PPP this has been done through the active and concrete support to National Coordinators by providing them with a rich source of background materials, sharing examples from other countries' successful processes, and convening them in regular meetings for exchange and updates, helping in their roadmap and funding application writing, and even personal visits to support their national processes. Some countries have indeed joined forces between two or more RIs to apply for roadmap status or funding thereafter. eLTER is in joint consortia with LifeWatch (the Netherlands), with ICOS, ACTRIS and AnaEE (Finland), LifeWatch, ICOS, DISSCo and GBIF (Portugal), to mention few.

3.2 Priority strategic relationships of eLTER RI in Europe

3.2.1 Overview

The environmental RI landscape has developed in many phases during several ESFRI Roadmap periods since the first Roadmap in 2006. It is clear that all environmental RIs have to work out their own specific profiles and competences, and in doing so, also actively search for collaboration and complementarities (see Figure 8, Figure 9).

Figure 8: The complementary roles as well as the services the environmental RIs provide to diverse user communities. The central part represents the complementary and interoperable in-situ networks for standardised large scale observations (ICOS, ACTRIS), natural and socio-ecological systems research (LTER, DANUBIUS) and experimentation (AnaEE, AQUACOSM). These in-situ infrastructures provide data for the infrastructures above, dealing with modelling, data analysis and workflow automation (e.g. LifeWatch) and supporting system understanding, predictions and decision-making. Modelling and analyses feed their parameter requirements back to the data generating units. All RIs should make use of generic supporting e-infrastructures and reference infrastructures such as EUDAT, EOSC and DiSSCo (in the bottom). Scientific and other user communities (at the top) will benefit from the cooperating RIs. Figure modified and updated from the eLTER Design Study, 2018.

Figure 9: detailed operational links and interactions between eLTER and sister-RIs and projects. The linkages with in-situ RIs (ICOS, UNECE-WGE components, DANUBIUS, EMBRC/AQUACOSM, AnaEE) relate to co-location and harmonisation of parameters and methods, whereas collaboration with the generic and e-infrastructures is important in developing e.g. semantics and data flows, management, and storage (DiSSCo, LifeWatch, EUDAT). Figure modified and updated from the eLTER Design Study, 2018.

eLTER has actively pursued discussions and developed concepts for better integration of the components in the environmental RI domain. The bilateral consultations have led to designing of Letters of Support or Memoranda of Understanding between eLTER and other RIs and networks.

Table 2 shows the current status of relationships with the European peers and some networks.

Table 2: eLTER-initiated actions towards coordination and collaboration between RIs and networks. MoU = Memorandum of Understanding, MoC=Memorandum of Collaboration, LoS= Letter of Support.

RI/network	Key action towards collaboration agreement/implementation	Status
ICOS	Formal collaboration offer Co-location opportunities explored Joint scientific sessions	Approved by ICOS GA, 2021-05, formal response pending EGU2021
AnaEE	Dialogue about collaboration, draft MoC	Dialogue ongoing
LifeWatch	MoU experts meeting on IT planned	2017 MoU existing, 2021 update in preparation
Danubius	MoU	In preparation In preparation

	Position paper and suggested activities at pilot sites	
ICP Forests	MoU	In preparation
Aquacosm	Support letter Joint concept paper	Provided in 2018 In preparation
UNECE Working Group of Effects (WGE)	MoC	Final negotiations
Mountain Research Initiative	Participation as Associate Partner in Preparatory Phase through ETH Zürich	In preparation
DiSSCo	eLTER participated in Infrastructure Contact Zones analysis Trilateral MoC with GBIF envisaged	In preparation
Jerico	LoS Joint concept paper	Ready (2020) In preparation
INTERACT	Harmonization of site attributes in DEIMS SDR	Ready
Programme on Ecosystem Change and Society	Presentation of eLTER RI to PECS board in 2020	Initial dialogue done
MAB - Man and the Environment Biosphere Initiative	Initial contact made; discussion to share spatial data to assess site overlap (in context of ILTER)	Initial dialogue done
NATURA network	Presentation of eLTER made to network; ongoing discussion of collaboration potential	Ongoing discussion

3.3 Characteristics and status of interactions with priority peers in Europe

As shown above, eLTER has been actively seeking synergies with other environmental RIs and related networks in Europe and globally. Here we summarise some of the closest relationships and the status of formal agreements between sister-RIs and eLTER.

Several of these relationships were analyzed on the basis of the ENVRplus RI-RI-consultation scheme, which was leadingly developed by eLTER and aims at identifying collaboration potential and concretizing existing and potential RI-RI interactions on the basis of a set of characteristics and criteria. Concluding from the analyses summarized above, the following sections outline the status of interactions with peers, with whom mutual benefits are most probable and the need for harmonizing designs, achieving complementarity and collaborating wherever reasonable is highest.

3.3.1 Research infrastructures and RI initiatives

3.3.1.1 ICOS

The European Integrated Carbon Observatory System (ICOS ERIC) and eLTER fill complementary niches in the European RI landscape. ICOS measures and reports terrestrial ecosystem and oceanic carbon (C) and greenhouse gas (GHG) budgets as well as resulting atmospheric concentrations and fluxes. In the ecosystem domain, ICOS has realised

harmonised and standardised measurements of C and GHG budgets, building on more than 70 flux towers in (currently) 12 European countries (6 of them also signatories of eLTER EoS). The ICOS ecosystem community has developed detailed measurement protocols and provided standardised site instructions for many parameters. Furthermore, it has an established process of site labelling.

The goals of the ICOS and eLTER Research Infrastructures (RIs) are complementary, not competitive. The ICOS ecosystem measurements, protocols and data have clear synergies with eLTER. The eLTER RI concept embodies the ENVIplus co-location and inter-operational approach between different RIs, specifically at the Master Sites. Having collaboration and integration as core pillars of the eLTER vision and mission highlights the deep commitment to co-location, with each RI operating at a site making the measurements to which it is best suited. This commitment can, however, cause confusion. The eLTER RI does not aim to cover the whole spectrum of ecosystem-related observations on its own but instead sees and promotes the co-design and co-development of services delivered by multiple co-located RIs.

The underlying eLTER theoretical observation concept, which is based on Ecosystem Integrity, and the eLTER conceptual model combining Press Pulse Dynamics (PPD, horizontal component) and macrosystems ecology (MSE, vertical component) together aim at a comprehensive understanding of ecosystems that includes observations made by multiple RIs (e.g., the ICOS Ecosystem network, eLTER, etc.) of the C cycle and the impact of climate change on productivity or GHG emissions from terrestrial ecosystems. The eLTER commitment to co-design, co-development and co-location does not imply conceptual overlap with the ICOS Ecosystem network but instead highlights the added value that can be achieved on a practical level by cross-RI cooperation. Additional observations carried out by eLTER RI at ICOS sites e.g. on the nitrogen (N) cycle, biodiversity or pollutants will be scientifically extremely valuable for the interpretation of core parameters observed by ICOS while, *vice versa*, the ICOS competence on C and GHG observations and information management provide valuable inputs into the eLTER RI. Furthermore, eLTER studies on regional emissions complement ICOS activities in this field.

Unlike ICOS, the eLTER RI concept includes regional multi- and transdisciplinary case study areas (eLTSER Platforms), comprising multiple spatially-nested smaller scale elements for socio-ecological research. The eLTSER Platforms incorporate human dimensions of environmental change, which are extremely useful both for identifying societal drivers and constraints on GHG budgets (e.g., changes in agricultural N use or changes in forest management) and for assessing societal impacts of a changing C cycle (e.g., changes in income of primary producers due to drought effects on yield).

With integration of these two RIs, Europe could provide a broad range of long-term observations on terrestrial ecosystems. In a nutshell, integration efforts could cover the following fields:

- 1.) Promoting Cooperative Master Sites in the National Networks of ICOS and eLTER: This will bring clear and significant added scientific value in the form of comprehensive and systematic observations, common data evaluation and modelling approaches by user communities, as well as a possibility to reduce site construction and operating costs. The German TERENO network is an example of this. Co-design of measurement strategies to include clear responsibilities for both the ICOS Ecosystem Thematic Centre (ETC) and eLTER ensured that both RIs are contributing to joint scientific aims.

- 2.) Further co-development and implementation of e-infrastructures, data services and data integration platforms (see also EUDAT): Previously, the ICOS RI has taken a leading role in clustering e-infrastructure and data management efforts for environmental RIs in the

framework of the H2020 project ENVRIplus. Since eLTER was already active in the FP7 cluster project ENVRI and the Horizon 2020 follow-up ENVRIplus, and is currently very active in ENVRIfair, this is an excellent opportunity for deepening cross-RI data interoperability. The goal here is to overcome fragmentation by co-developing and promoting e-infrastructures and data services as suggested by ENVRIplus and piloted by ENVRIfair.

3.) Conceptual and technical developments: Theoretical approaches as well as measurement techniques used in ICOS and eLTER share common roots, with synergies to be expected from cooperation in these fields. As an example, reactive N flux measurements with eddy covariance technology (Ferrara et al. 2012, Brümmer et al. 2013, Zöll et al. 2016) could be an excellent field of cooperation.

Options for strengthening interactions between eLTER and ICOS

Together, ICOS and eLTER have started working on a pilot strengthening of such options, including exploring possibilities for co-enhancing their RIs by a clear division of tasks, and mutually complementing their site networks across the current geopolitical coverage of each partner. Currently, the most feasible way forwards appears to be in-depth cooperation of structurally independent entities. This approach would build on the existing ICOS and eLTER infrastructures and deepen the existing cooperation in the areas of co-location, methodological standardisation and data interoperability that has already started in ENVRIplus. Platforms such as GEOSS could be used for common metadata catalogues.

In depth cooperation of structurally independent entities would not require large organisational changes for either ICOS or eLTER. Both RIs could continue their internal integration and work towards respective grand challenges, and respond flexibly to upcoming new demands.

The main disadvantage of this option is the insufficient geographic coverage of the two RIs across Europe and the consequent competition for membership and resources. However, ongoing competition on membership (on the European level) and resources (on the national level), could be addressed by a novel generation of smart agreements towards European RI integration: The vision could be, e.g., that the “ICOS module” as part of eLTER RI’s “whole system approach” is compliant and taken care of by ICOS, either as a formal ICOS site or via association with ICOS. In a similar manner, focal components of eLTER (complementary biogeochemical cycles components, less intensive approaches for assessing C cycle components at larger scales or Regular Sites, biodiversity, socio-ecology) covered at ICOS sites could be formal or associated eLTER sites.

This field needs further exploration with clear descriptions of scientific, methodological and technical core competences of the individual RIs in order to avoid duplication of effort. For example, while the ICOS Ecosystem Thematic Centre has a world-leading position in the processing and quality assurance and control of eddy covariance-based flux measurements, the eLTER RI holds the same position in integrating N cycle and biodiversity observations, research on other pollutants/drivers and on socio-ecological interactions. To overcome unnecessary competition and find parallel competences, a cross-RI system of services needs to be built. Co-design, development and implementation of such a system would unlock enormous resources and drastically improve the science if mutual services could be realised.

As stated above, a core task in both RIs is the harmonisation of standard variables. This requires a huge community effort but would contribute to a clear definition of the niches of each partner and a clear description of the European Research Area in the domain.

3.3.1.1.1 Piloting collaboration at co-located sites

In chapter 3.1.1 we summarized the outcomes of the ENVRIplus task 12.3 (Kutsch et al. 2017), elaborating options for co-location or even co-management of RIs (Kutsch et al. 2017). Such “Collaborative Master Sites” (see Figure 10) do have the potential to explore ecosystems with the cumulative set of instrumentations and expertise of two or more RIs.

Figure 10: Concept for hierarchical co-location between different Research Infrastructures in the Ecosystem/Biodiversity domain. Different symbols represent different core measurements from different Research Infrastructures. Cooperative ENVRI Master Sites (CEMS) are the highest level of scientific integration and co-location. Co-location between two or three Research Infrastructures may also be very useful. Source: Kutsch et al 2017.

Given the obvious proximity and necessity for close interactions between ICOS and LTER, the eLTER PLUS project incorporated a small bilateral eLTER-ICOS pilot for for such an ambitious general integration endeavour, which will contribute implementation options (scientific, technical, and operational aspects) to further and concretized collaborations. The plans and first results were reported in a dedicated scientific session of EGU 2021 (convener: Martyn Futter, SLU, Sweden).

3.3.1.1.2 Concrete steps towards formalized collaboration

Building on the long history of interactions, collaborations in other projects contexts and the work on the eLTER PLUS pilot, eLTER formally approached the ICOS General Assembly in a letter suggesting more formal collaboration steps in April 2021.

The practical suggestion was to establish joint expert working groups to elaborate concrete options in areas comprising

- standard observations and interlinked responsibilities for certain groups of variables
- collaboration at jointly used sites

- network design and RI-level strategic collaborations

eLTER expressed its hope that the findings of the working groups could be condensed in overall strategic collaboration options at the RI level to then feed into the respective planning and decision-making processes.

The ICOS General Assembly accepted the offer and agreed in principle to the suggestions (communication by the ICOS DG), but a formal response is still pending (October 2021).

3.3.1.2 AnaEE

The Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems RI (AnaEE), placed in the Health and Food domain of the ESFRI roadmap, is designed to develop experimental facilities to subject managed and unmanaged ecosystems to expected future conditions and states and to ascertain the role of individual forcing variables and their interactions on ecosystems processes. AnaEE's experimental approach includes state-of-the-science experimental manipulation facilities and process-level measurements, to statistical studies and models. Replicated experiments can be paired in both controlled environments (enclosed platforms) and natural *in-situ* conditions (open-air platforms) throughout Europe, being co-located with other existing long-term observational networks such as eLTER, which are providing high-quality data to parameterise experimental models and to extrapolate beyond the boundary of the experiment itself. When operational, AnaEE foresees > 100 national platforms across Europe, many of them co-located with eLTER NRIs.

Linking AnaEE results with data from observational sites across Europe (ICOS, LTER) will allow models to be rigorously tested and scaled to larger geographical areas. AnaEE will also complement and add value to emerging research infrastructures in the agrifood, forestry, bioenergy and aquaculture sectors.

Previously, eLTER and AnaEE have worked together in the EU FP7 project ExpeER (Experimentation in Ecosystem Research) which was built on several FP initiatives (e.g. Climmani, AnaEE), networks (e.g. LTER) and projects (e.g. EnvEurope). In ExpeER, a joint conceptual model for highly instrumented research sites was developed, indicating clear and highly complementary roles for both the experimental (AnaEE) and observational (eLTER) RIs.

The ExpeER pyramid represents the conceptual elements of the FP7 ExpeER project, comprising of Ecotrons, Highly Instrumented Experimental research sites, Highly Instrumented Observational research sites, modeling and analytical platforms. The hierarchical design of ExpeER (see Figure 11) also recommended strategic interactions between these actual research infrastructures and larger scale monitoring schemes in three major fields: (i) Consistent design and lobbying, (ii) Concerted contributions to scientific targets, (iii) Joint use of tools.

Figure 11: Hierarchy of ExpeER elements with AnaEE and eLTER specially positioned as complementing each other.

The harmonized implementation of the building blocks of the landscape will support highly integrated national ecosystem research infrastructure clusters, their efficient multiple use towards scientific targets and the joint development of further services, called upon in many European countries. Both, eLTER and AnaEE are depending on a number of data generating facilities. While the focus of AnaEE is on experimental manipulation of a wide range of different ecosystem drivers, in order to describe their present and potential future role for ecosystem functioning, eLTER focuses on long-term observations. Both approaches are highly needed and also highly complementary, and both benefit from cooperative developments, including data sharing and transfer, data standards and protocols, semantic capabilities, and supporting software. Furthermore, AnaEE and eLTER work at different spatial scales which are interconnected and there is a potential for mutual benefits of co-locating eLTER sites with AnaEE sites. Finally, eLTER undertakes a strong socioecological approach which may be combined with the experimental data obtained by AnaEE on the potential future responses of ecosystems to changes in a range of pressures, in order to create new and better adaptation strategies to future global changes.

In future, the collaboration between AnaEE and eLTER will be developed especially under the ENVRI Ecosystem domain, where integration and collaboration tools are jointly pursued. The possible cooperative activities between eLTER and AnaEE include three main areas: consistent design and lobbying, concerted contributions to scientific targets, and common tools and services. The first one includes, e.g., encouraging a close interaction of national eLTER partners and AnaEE national nodes; fostering co-location and the joint use of basic infrastructures; and ensuring efficient two-way communication on activities and joint publicity to audiences in support of these cooperative activities. The scientific collaboration includes, e.g., developing collaborative research projects requiring both comprehensive long-term observations and targeted experimentation, creating jointly scientific sessions and training workshops at national and European wide conferences and events, and common synthesis workshops. The common tools and services, i.e. the operational collaboration includes e.g., fostering interoperability towards a service-oriented architecture, for which the

LifeWatch/ENVRplus Reference Model may serve as guidance; promoting the use of common standards and protocols; engaging to a common, free and open access data and software policy; co-operation in the field of controlled vocabularies for ecosystem research (EnvThes), site documentation (DEIMS-SDR) and parameter prioritisation (EcoPAR); and finally participation in joint expert groups, together with other related RIs such as ICOS.

3.3.1.3 DANUBIUS

The ESFRI project **DANUBIUS-RI** (International Centre for Advanced Studies on River–Sea Systems) will be a pan-European distributed research infrastructure dedicated to interdisciplinary studies of mainly larger river–sea systems. It will enable and support research addressing the conflicts between society's demands, environmental change and environmental protection in river–sea systems worldwide. Discussions about roles and interactions were launched during ICRI2016 at the RI coordination level. With active contributions from DANUBIUS experts from Germany and Austria, this exchange resulted in the shared view that there is the potential for mutually beneficial cooperation with a clear division of tasks related to the spatial scale. While the eLTER RI focusses on LTER Sites and LTSER Platforms of about 1 km² (vast majority) to 1000 km² (50 Platforms), DANUBIUS covers river systems, sediment transport and impact on coasts and the sea at a larger scale. A clear interaction will consist of harmonising observations and parameters to secure downstream interoperability of information produced at eLTER *in-situ* facilities. Options for cooperation at DANUBIUS SuperSites/eLTER Master Sites in terms of co-location or co-management need to be explored once the NRIs have been clarified. Mutual consultations on standards (e.g. metadata) as well as existing and planned IT services will form an important part of a first cooperation phase.

The next agreed step with DANUBIUS is to exemplify site co-location alongside 4 best examples, - including the Venice lagoon (IT), Danube delta (RO) and Watercluster Lunz (AT).

3.3.1.4 Aquacosm

AQUACOSM (2017-2021) and **AQUACOSM-plus** (2020-2024) “**Network of Leading Ecosystem Scale Experimental AQUatic MesoCOSM Facilities Connecting Rivers, Lakes, Estuaries and Oceans in Europe and beyond**” are advanced community H2020 research infrastructures that was initiated by the marine network EU FP7 MESOAQUA network project (2009-2012). The substantial expanded AQUACOSM-plus network now comprises leading aquatic experimental facilities from all aquatic realms (freshwater, coastal & marine, standing & running waters). With the expansion to 31 partners and over 60 mesocosm facilities, AQUACOSM-plus covers all major climatic and biogeographic zones across Europe (see Figure 12). Nevertheless, the number of AQUACOSM sites are limited compared to the number of eLTER sites. However, advanced facilities that allows effective empirical work on large, sometimes ecosystem level, are dependent on both substantial economical investments and skills, thus the use of these are relatively limited. Therefore, the network makes such advanced aquatic experimental facilities available to scientists and other users, to address urgent scientific and societal issues at the most suitable experimental facilities.

Besides offering access to RI-facilities the AQUACOSM network has many similarities with eLTER such as developing joint site designs, internationally coordinated investigations and developing a suite of harmonized novel methodology and operations, but with the difference that the AQUACOSM network focuses solely on experiential facilities in aquatic environments. The mutual and highly complementary localizations and scientific strengths between the AQUACOSM and eLTER represents a substantial potential for direct collaboration, that both networks therefore plan to explore. This exploration will initially be facilitated by that many of

the AQUACOSM sites are already co-located with eLTER-sites. As many members in both networks are also involved in numerous other H2020 projects, such as eLTER PLUS, JERICO, and ICOS, a wider cross-RI collaboration is also planned as a key goal for AQUACOSM-plus. Thus, rather than adding another infrastructure on the ESFRI roadmap, AQUACOSM-plus aims at generating synergies together with other RI projects.

Figure 12: AQUACOSM-plus partners and their mesocosm facilities in biogeographical regions in Europe. Large red dots show main partner locations. Small red points connected with dashed lines denote location of distributed facilities (SITES AquanET in Sweden, INRA-LIFE in France, IBERIAN Pond Network (IBN) in Portugal & Spain). Stars show the locations of three SMEs and one NGO.

Specifically, for the case of eLTER and AQUACOSM, long-term observations are necessary to become aware about changes in habitats and ecological communities, and to formulate hypotheses, while targeted experiments are designed to test the hypotheses and study underlying mechanisms. Thus, for a most effective development of our understanding of the ecosystems as well as our ability to predict and best manage the future, these approaches must be effectively unified. Multiple sites in AQUACOSM are eLTER sites, we therefore want to use the opportunity to showcase the added value of RI-RI collaboration at selected sites in AQUACOSM & eLTER.

The current Roadmap position and preparatory phase of eLTER RI provides excellent opportunities for designing and implementing the operations in future, and there is also good potential for co-design the services for the needs of experimental aquatic research. Therefore, the synergies and added value of joint operations in long-term observations and experimentation in ecosystems will be piloted by eLTER PLUS and AQUACOSM-plus. This includes e.g., strategic planning, design of sites and platforms, training and networking at site and RI level, and reciprocal development of joint instrumentation and standards for observations. A specific aim is to initiate this process by investigating the feasibility of coordination of science and/or TA activity at already closely located sites.

3.3.1.5 JERICO

JERICO-RI (Joint European Research Infrastructure of Coastal Observatories) is an integrated pan-European multidisciplinary and multi-platform research infrastructure dedicated to a holistic appraisal of coastal marine system changes. It is seamlessly bridging existing continental, atmospheric and open ocean RIs, thus filling a key gap in the ESFRI

landscape. JERICO-RI establishes the framework upon which coastal marine systems are observed, analysed, understood and forecasted. JERICO-RI enables open-access to state-of-the-art and innovative facilities, resources, FAIR data and fit-for-purpose services, fostering international science collaboration.

The ambition of JERICO-RI to deliver the key elements to reach a comprehensive understanding of the responses of marine coastal ecosystem to climate changes and anthropogenic stressors is complementary with objectives of eLTER, which comprises sites from the cryosphere to the coast (terrestrial, freshwater and transitional waters), for the coastal marine domain. Of particular relevance to JERICO is the organization of the observation space of the coastal region. The same applies to eLTER on the continent. Both are developing a distributed infrastructure of sites (stationary observations) and mobile platforms according to the specificities of the habitats they deal with.

Consequently, there is a high interest in maximizing synergies and organizing smart handover point between the two RIs, e.g. concerning processes alongside the land-sea continuum and related interoperable observation systems. Clusters of nearby located eLTER and JERICO sites were already identified and have a high potential in identifying and further developing RI-RI collaborations. These collaborations might comprise IT tools co-design, co-development and co-use, metadata and ontologies, instrumentation, logistical issues like the combination of long-term stations with mobile platforms, education and training (IT, site management, whole systems approach), conceptual work on RI collaborations and integrations at the European scale, and alignment of strategies both at the European scale and mirrored national alignments.

3.3.1.6 LifeWatch

The LifeWatch and eLTER RI ongoing efforts are closely linked in the majority of countries that are involved in both RIs. Lifewatch ERIC advances biodiversity and ecosystem research by providing knowledge-based solutions to environmental managers, and by providing access to a multitude of datasets, services and tools enabling the construction and operation of virtual research environments where specific issues related with biodiversity, and ecosystem research and preservation are addressed. As LifeWatch is a virtual infrastructure concentrating on biodiversity data, it complements the eLTER *in-situ* infrastructures in many ways.

The provision of LifeWatch services to users already depends on a number of data generating *in-situ* facilities including eLTER NRIs. In turn, eLTER is a potential user of the LifeWatch ERIC e-services. Both benefit from cooperative developments, including data sharing and transfer, data standards and protocols, semantic capabilities, and supporting software. The framework for cooperative and collaborative work between eLTER and LifeWatch recognises their respective independent yet complementary missions.

Cooperative activities can include, among others:

- a. promotion of a common, free and open access data and software policy;
- b. fostering interoperability by cooperation towards a service-oriented architecture for which the LifeWatch Reference Model may serve as guidance;
- c. fostering the use of common ontologies, standards and protocols;
- d. development of joint demand-driven data discovery and mobilisation plans involving eLTER NRIs and LifeWatch National Centres;
- e. ensuring the interoperability of the eLTER RI architecture and the LifeWatch

- architecture;
- f. identifying and implementing collaborative projects of value to both organisations;
 - g. establishing a mechanism to secure the continued maintenance and improvement of cooperation to meet common goals;
 - h. developing joint thematic or training workshops and other meetings, both at the European and national levels;
 - i. promoting the participation of European countries in both Parties by encouraging a close interaction of national eLTER NRI and LifeWatch National Centres;
 - j. ensuring frequent two-way communication on activities and joint publicity to audiences in support of these cooperative activities.

For this ESFRI proposal, LifeWatch ERIC provided a statement (dated July 31, 2017), which is still valid concerning future directions:

“The ‘Long-Term Research on Ecosystems in Europe (eLTER)’ initiative, to be presented for its inclusion in the ESFRI 2018 Roadmap, aims [at] the continuous collection, provisioning and use of ecosystem data from long-term environmental observation sites. This will enable to identify drivers of ecosystem changes in response to global pressures and the impacts of multiple stressors on natural resources, ecosystems and biodiversity.

LifeWatch ERIC understands that this data could be very relevant for the creation of virtual research environments devoted to evaluate the impact of such stressors on biodiversity and to support the decision-making of environmental managers based on scientific knowledge. Therefore, the General Assembly expresses its willingness to seek potential synergies with this initiative to cooperate and promote the study of biodiversity, while avoiding duplication of efforts in their respective areas of work.

In 2020 a process towards an updated MoC was started between the LifeWatch and eLTER coordination. The plan is to keep the actual MoC slim and foresee regular annexes on concrete collaborative activities. To that end we plan for an experts workshop between the eLTER Service Portfolio and IT services developers late in 2021 or early in 2022.

3.3.1.7 DiSSCo

The **DiSSCo** (Distributed System of Scientific Collections) initiative is at the ESFRI Roadmap since 2018. In DiSSCo, the emphasis is on bio- and geodiversity data sources and collections. eLTER and DiSSCo are complementary in their shared focus on long-term data on biodiversity (among others). eLTER RI will provide data on selected parameters of *in-situ* biodiversity and their site-specific historical trends, while DiSSCo will make data available from scientific collections across Europe, providing taxonomic and other references of high relevance for any long-term and legacy biodiversity data and specimens. Both initiatives together form a robust baseline for environmental studies and their collaboration greatly contributes to a more solid, precise and contrasted source of information to any third party. At the moment the process of DiSSCo RI is still in its initial phases and it is difficult to conclude how eLTER RI would collaborate with it, however, realising the potential of large historical datasets which are existing e.g. in eLTER RI, it is very likely that joint activities and complementarities can be developed based on the good interaction and collaboration in developing the ENVRplus RI-RI consultation scheme.

3.3.2 Integration into existing monitoring schemes to yield policy-relevant information

In many cases, environmental RIs like eLTER RI also provide fundamental long-term monitoring information, e.g. on the effects of air pollutants, water quality and productivity of agricultural and forest ecosystems. Furthermore, their data may also contribute to the surveillance of international agreements (e.g. UNFCCC Kyoto and Paris agreements, CLRTAP protocols, Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)) and to assessing their implementation. The usefulness of an RI to users other than researchers depends on how well their higher-level products and services are planned and communicated. The results of these public monitoring systems are used in the different policies of member states and also serve as long-term datasets for high-level research, adding value to the activities when planned and implemented in a coordinated manner.

A key factor in the initiation of eLTER RI in Europe concerns strategic demands made by bodies responsible for environmental monitoring, such as the European Environment Agency (EEA), currently challenged by multiple global and regional crises (energy, climate, food, financial) and requiring knowledge-based support for decision making. Many of the added values of permanent infrastructure for ecosystem and critical zone research relate to requirements linked to the challenges of environmental monitoring, reporting, integrated assessment and valuation of ecosystem services, e.g.:

1. Indicator validation and development across scales, environmental and socio-ecological gradients
2. Optimisation of monitoring schemes (scale-explicit, nested designs) across compartments and sectors
3. Policy support through assessing effects of measures (e.g. conservation measures on the (sub-) regional level within and outside protected areas) and verification of international treaties (e.g. Paris agreement stipulations on climate change and carbon stocks in forests)
4. Accurate estimates of quality and quantity of natural resources and the ecosystem services they provide.

Three main aspects will determine to what extent these values will become fully effective in the mid- and long-term:

- A) Ensuring major policy-relevant research projects are well-embedded within the European Research Area and capitalising on eLTER central services. The results of these projects themselves will contribute to the hot-spot nature of individual sites in all eLTER NRIs in terms of information density, data availability and understanding of complex phenomena (expertise) at a pan-European scale. This is a self-reinforcing process which will significantly raise the cost-benefit ratio of any type of information gathered
- B) The focused ecosystem- and socio-ecological research in the eLTER RI is linked with systematic European environmental monitoring programmes and will be adding value to them by providing legacy datasets, increasing the reliability of collected data and adding a selection of usable parameters for assessing monitoring results
- C) The functional (parameter sets, data), spatial (design) and temporal (real-time) integration of in-situ networks and the coordinated provision of central services will ensure cost-efficient, seamless availability of data across environmental or administrative boundaries. This includes enabling harmonised public access points for data and metadata across legal and funding frameworks.

The proposed eLTER RI catalyses progress in all three areas.

The eLTER site network already contains numerous site nodes providing links with large scale monitoring schemes like GLORIA and the UNECE WGE International Co-operative Programmes (LoS from ICP Integrated Monitoring and ICP Forests). For example, altogether 42 countries and ca. 300 experts participate in the ICP Forests Programme, and thus there is a large existing user group. With 80 forested sites that are also partners in ICP programmes, the eLTER RI builds on impressive achievements of these harmonisation and standardisation activities and “RI development” over decades, when the notion of “Research Infrastructures” had not yet been developed or applied to distributed environmental RIs. It is a mutual benefit to be able to utilise these sites more efficiently, and to support the sustained and expanding use of this invaluable data collection. Chapter 3.3.2.1 below expands on the current efforts towards a MoC with the UNECE WGE.

Once eLTER Sites and eLTSER Platforms in particular have been integrated within monitoring schemes, they can provide the ecosystem- and socioecological context of individual monitoring and sampling points (e.g. EMEP, ICP IM, ICOS). Capitalising on the contextual data gathered at different scales in nested designs, as promoted by eLTER, via multivariate statistics, geostatistical methods and stratifications, will help in quantifying the power and representativity of point data as well as their proper utility in models, e.g. for the testing of scenarios.

Developing standard observations and measurements for the eLTER RI underpinned the mutual interdependency and complementarity of long-term ecosystem research and monitoring (LTEM). The discussion about standard observations will, along with achieving proper coverage of Europe’s socio-ecological zones, also impact recommendations concerning the selection of further sites in the eLTER NRIs.

This relates to the question of how environmental monitoring and research are organised in Europe: Although the responsibility for research rests mainly with universities and other academic institutions, generally environmental monitoring is carried out by governmental bodies. Yet funding mechanisms, mandates, internal organisation and self-perception of staff roles favour either: i) the production of high quality long-term monitoring data, applied research and the maintenance of infrastructure or ii) scientific projects and teaching. Where monitoring is defined as the continuous observation, control and measuring of the state and structure of a system, research is the planned and targeted search for new findings in a specific realm. But applying a longer timescale, the designs and targets of monitoring are hypothesis-driven as well. The recent reorganisation of LTER in the United States and interactions with NEON (www.neoninc.org) gives evidence that there is no LTER without LTEM and *vice versa*. Environmental research needs to trigger and optimise monitoring designs and methods and mutually-produced monitoring data must form an integral part of the research. eLTER’s design provides a step towards integration and the synergistic use of potentials and division of tasks. In this sense, it is of high importance that both the eLTER H2020 project and the eLTER RI have close links with US LTER and US NEON, and the Australian national integrated Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network, TERN, to incorporate best available knowledge and circumnavigate known pitfalls in this process.

3.3.2.1 UNECE Working Group on Effects

The eLTER RI will be ca. 200 selected sites covering all biogeographical zones in Europe, where biological, biogeochemical, hydrological and socio-ecological data will be collected. This network will be recruited from the existing 460 accredited LTER Europe sites. Currently, 110 of these sites belong to the ICP’s network of International Collaborative Programmes (ICPs on Forest, Water, Vegetation and Integrated Monitoring) of the WGE Working Group of Effects (WGE) of the UNECE Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution (CLRTAP). The implementation of the eLTER RI has had and will have consequences for the WGE monitoring networks at the national as well as the Pan-European scale. With a “letter of

cooperation” (LoC), we aim at defining ways of cooperation between the bodies of the Convention and the eLTER RI in order to render benefits and synergies for both networks. Due to the big number of members and participants in WGE activities, the process towards LoC has been ongoing since 2018, but is now close to be finished.

Key areas of cooperation addressed in the LoC are Site infrastructure (Long-term ecosystem observation and research site network, standard observations, IT services, data integration, scientific support for policy makers, synergies and collaborations at the national scale, mutual invitation to meetings and policy outreach:

The CLRTAP has, for many years, set the standards regarding monitoring and reporting of ecosystem effects of air pollution with their manuals and protocols. The eLTER RI will take advantage of these existing knowledge and standards wherever suitable and feasible in order to guarantee consistent long-term time series. To leverage benefits for both partners further collaboration will be necessary when developing the broader suite of Standard Observations that the eLTER RI is aiming for. Collaboration between eLTER and the program centres of the ICPs of the WGE should seek effective ways to share data and data services. We encourage exploring cooperation such as those existing between eLTER and ICP Forests (e.g. ICP Forests will register all sites at DEIMS). The scientific bodies of the CLRTAP provide fact based information for air pollution policies. Research at the eLTER RI also aims at supporting policies to improve the state of the environment and the sustainable use of ecosystems and biodiversity. Since environmental change effects on ecosystems are rarely independent from each other, exchanging knowledge and bundling communication efforts can lead to better policies. Joint actions at the science-policy interface have a high potential for increased impact. The monitoring sites under the WGE are managed and funded through national centres. The same applies to the National Research Infrastructure components of eLTER RI. The WGE centres and the national eLTER NRI coordinators could cooperate closer in order to improve the quality and long-term sustainability of their sites through strategic alignment.

3.3.2.2 Observations in Arctic regions

As the ongoing climate change is fastest in the northern and Arctic areas and the ecosystems and societies are already experiencing huge changes, the long-term, systematic observations and a build-up of knowledge on its climate and environment are crucially needed. The observed higher air and sea temperatures cause dramatic changes in vegetation distribution, atmospheric and ocean circulation, thinning of sea ice, and thawing of permafrost with immense local and regional consequences. While the environmental changes and the resulting threats are great as such, also the economic exploitation in the Arctic is increasing and putting the societies in totally new situation.

eLTER is extending through the whole European continent, from the Atlantic Ocean to Black Sea and from the Mediterranean to the Arctic. LTER-Europe site coverage is densest in Central Europe for many historical reasons, but nevertheless, also in the boreal, subarctic and Arctic areas in Finland, Sweden and Norway several tens of sites are existing as part of the LTER-Europe network. In addition to their long-term ecological data collection, many Arctic sites are actively working with citizen science initiatives and pursuing other stakeholder engagement e.g. with indigenous peoples and local communities. Many of the Arctic and subarctic LTER sites are operating already for many decades, some even >100 years, providing a unique opportunity for researchers in e.g. biodiversity, ecosystem functioning and socio-ecological research.

Many northern eLTER sites are participating in national or international networks and projects such as INTAROS, EU-POLARnet or INTERACT, which provide tools and services to access the Arctic sites and their data for research and other stakeholders. INTERACT is a circumpolar network of currently 89 terrestrial field bases in northern Europe, Russia, US, Canada, Greenland, Iceland, the Faroe Islands and Scotland as well as stations in northern alpine

areas, and ca 20 LTER sites in Scandinavia, Scotland and Finland are co-located with INTERACT. These sites represent the total environmental envelope of the North, from the coniferous forest of the taiga in the south to the inland ice sheet on Greenland, for research and monitoring.

The collaboration opportunities in the Arctic region are, e.g., in site cataloguing in DEIMS SDR and services for researchers looking for access to sites, data harmonization and management, harmonizing the vocabularies and observation systems and providing site managers improved operational tools in challenging environments. Currently the INTERACT stations are listed in DEIMS SDR, and in this way collaboration opportunities can be already promoted. The Arctic collaboration is also providing eLTER an opportunity to engage the Russian field sites in the Arctic and subarctic region, which are participating in the Arctic networks.

3.3.3 Service providers of RI relevance

3.3.3.1 EUDAT

eLTER belongs to the main user communities of EUDAT services (adopted MoC and provisioning of LTER use cases in several countries). The eLTER work towards data and metadata integration will benefit from the existing data-oriented e-infrastructures and national services involved, allowing cost-efficient use of investments already made for e-infrastructures. It is also imperative to align with selections and data policies adopted at the European level. For example, eLTER is utilising EUDAT services for searching (B2FIND) and storing (B2SHARE) of data, for which integration into eLTER's international DEIMS database has started. eLTER plans are to develop DEIMS so that in the next release there will be RI-specific entry portals, allowing for RI-specific faceted search as currently implemented in the eLTER pilots.

There is a MoC between EUDAT and LTER-Europe, to be updated for eLTER RI during the PPP. EUDAT also provided an LoS for eLTER RI. The parties agree to collaborate on the following three tasks:

I. Requirement gathering:

This activity allows eLTER RI to submit new requirements to EUDAT and influence the evolution of the infrastructure and its services. EUDAT will accept requirements in various formats through the defined channels, either directly to members of the project, or via the EUDAT User Forums and other relevant events. Requirements will be presented and reviewed by the Service and Architecture Forum (SAF).

II. Service development

eLTER RI will be associated to the development of EUDAT services and be provided with the possibility to test and use the services which are seen of interest for the community. For example, eLTER is actively involved in the development of the semantic service through the Austrian NRI (EAA) as partner in EUDAT 1. Another example is the currently active collaboration between eLTER NRI in Finland (UHEL) and CSC in developing joint data platforms and APIs with the help of national RI funding. eLTER RI will provide an overview of the major workflows and required tools and services involved in long-term ecosystem research. Upon request, EUDAT services shall be checked for their relevance and usability for eLTER RI purposes. EUDAT will also consult eLTER RI regarding the development of new services to be included in the EUDAT service portfolio.

III. Dissemination and outreach

EUDAT and eLTER RI will collaborate and help each other in disseminating the progress and results from the collaboration between the two parties. This will involve featuring the projects on each other's websites and dissemination materials where appropriate, announcing each

other's events on the projects' websites and other dissemination material where appropriate, and more generally raising awareness of the projects in each other's communities. eLTER RI will also contribute to elaborate success stories and other dissemination material related to their use of EUDAT services.

3.4 Global peer relationships

Beyond Europe, eLTER makes s efforts to: (1) secure embedding in related international networks and infrastructure designs, (2) avoid duplication of conceptual efforts by considering best examples for integrated ecosystem research infrastructure designs, and (3) promote the use of approved EU policies, standards and best practices (e.g. open data policies, excellence-driven access to sites and effective data management).

Globally, eLTER is leadingly involved in the International LTER Network ILTER, as well as in the Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure GERI. The coordinator of eLTER is the co-chair of ILTER and chair of its International Collaborations Committee (ICC) and in this role represents ILTER and the eLTER component as formal GEO Participating Organization. The institution hosting the eLTER Head Office, UFZ/Germany, formally acts as signatory in the GERI partnership. Figure 13 provides an overview of current eLTER engagements.

Figure 13: eLTER concepts and services are designed for global usability. The figure shows relevant areas (left) and main global engagements.

In the first project phase (2020/2021) the activities of eLTER PPP were specifically constrained in the international work by the pandemic induced restrictions. However, based on intense work till March 2020 (incl. a fact finding mission with the key counterpart in Australia, TERN), some progress was made and the collaborations contributed to international virtual events of ILTER (Coordinating Committee), GERI (AGU, EGU) and GEO (through the e-shape project).

ILTER (International Long Term Ecological Research Network) is a network of networks, encompassing ca. 800 LTER research sites and ca. 70 LTSER platforms, located in a wide array of ecosystems that can help understand environmental change across the globe. ILTER's focus is on long-term, site-based research and monitoring in a globally distributed

network in the fields of ecosystem, biodiversity, critical zone and socio-ecological research. ILTER is a legal entity since 2007, and supported by membership fees by participating networks.

The LTER Europe network provides a majority of LTER sites and platforms globally (almost 60%). eLTER has been among the key contributors in ILTER, driving the development of ILTER to secure highest quality interoperable services in close interaction with the participating regional and global research infrastructures and networks. Majority of sites and platforms listed in DEIMS SDR, which also serves whole ILTER in addition to European ILTER component, are located in Europe, and the concept of 'Whole System Approach' was initiated from the vision of the LTER Europe network.

GERI (Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure): The European LTER belongs to a small number of ILTER partners leadingly working on advancing concepts, services, standards and organisational structure, *inter alia* in response to the framework for a coherent and coordinated world-wide development and operation of Global Research Infrastructures (GRI) elaborated by the Group of Senior Officials on Global Research Infrastructures (GSO 2013,). The GSO recognises the vital role of GRIs in addressing world-wide S&T challenges and the benefits of coordinating investments in global research infrastructures to efficiently use the available resources and fully realise their potential benefits. The interest in GRIs relies on its capacity to address the research needs of worldwide scientific communities by combining the best available knowledge, human capital and resources in one specific scientific area with multi-source funding. At the European scale, the eLTER RI design and planning responds to the 14 requirements as raised by GSO framework for RIs at the global scale, underpinning its importance and securing an important role in a further professionalised global LTER.

The GERI initiative comprises the site-based research infrastructures of its founding members, which are: CERN, eLTER, ICOS, NEON, SAEON and TERN. As a peer group, GERI is able to support the more efficient and structured development of eLTER RI. This effort reflects the current transition across many countries of observational networks and projects towards stable research infrastructures. The GERI founders advocate cooperation and common activities among Research Infrastructures that have already achieved a high internal organization and legal structure, but also exchange of experience with, and support for networks that have only recently started this process.

GERI emerged from several workshops among the founding members, where the development and governance processes, operational status and overarching goals of each GERI member were discussed. In these workshops, an overarching agreement was reached of the necessity to aim at complementary and harmonized observation stations in all continents.

The vision of the GERI is to provide and advocate a vision for a global Research Infrastructure providing terrestrial and coastal in-situ observations from a high number of observational sites, organized in a common hierarchical system and standardized in the highest possible degree. One of the eLTER contributions is to provide the agreed, common site registry (DEIMS-SDR) to document all GERI sites (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Site network of GERI partners (source: DEIMS-SDR, 2020).

GERI is dedicated to providing interoperable FAIR data that delivers a better understanding of the function and change of indicator ecosystems from terrestrial, freshwater and coastal environments across global biomes to support excellent science that can inform political and managerial decision-making addressing grand societal challenges (see Figure 15).

Figure 15: First assessment of the type and quantity of data products and data sets, which GERI partners can provide to areas of global change drivers and ecological processes.

The GERI partners agreed on a Memorandum of Understanding signed 2019-2020 by all founding members. The GERI governance and other matters are dealt with by working groups, along with guidelines to allow additional members to be recognised within the GERI framework. Appreciating the achievement and potential of GERI, the GSO formally approved GERI as a GSO Use Case in its meeting in Shanghai in December 2019, where GERI was presented.

The ILTER goals are compatible with the **Group on Earth Observation (GEO)** Strategic Plan 2016-2025, especially in terms of assuring sustainability of biodiversity and ecosystem services and determining the effects of climate change upon these; and in terms of contributing to the science evidence needed to achieve food security and sustainable agriculture under changing global climatic conditions. ILTER had already been involved in several GEO activities and initiatives (e.g. GEO ECO, GEOBON/GSEO) before it formally became a GEO Participating Organisation in 2016. Besides providing *in-situ* data, the large ILTER network represents an important and growing user community for GEO and thus increases the exploitation of data made accessible through GEO, thereby contributing to facilitating at least one of the eight Societal Benefit Areas "Biodiversity and Ecosystem Sustainability", and also to providing ecological insights into the cross-cutting area of SBAs, climate and carbon. provides an overview of eLTER/ILTER relevance and roles in the GEO context.

Figure 16: eLTER & ILTER ties to GEO

eLTER and ILTER sites, as part of a global platform for *in-situ* data, make a wide range of long-time series (several decades) accessible with supporting high quality essential information. These data will significantly enhance the overall GEO monitoring capabilities, fill existing information gaps, and will be complementary to many existing GEO data sets and especially to remote sensing data. Furthermore, for the latter, ILTER has the potential to become the foundation of high quality calibration and validation procedures at a global scale. These contributions from ILTER will help the GEO community to foster coordination of *in-situ* observations particularly for the terrestrial domain, and then to progress methods for linkage of *in-situ* observation and remote sensing. LTER in Europe collaborates nationally and/or at the continental scale with major projects related to GEO, e.g. EUBON, Connecting GEO/ENEON, GLOBIS-B and Copernicus. Since becoming a GEO Participating Organisation in 2016, ILTER has been strongly involved in the **GEO *in-situ* Task Group**, providing DEIMS as a pilot for a global observation site registry and participating in activities of a small core group to revive GTOS (Global Terrestrial Observation System). An interoperability check has been performed between DEIMS and the **GEO Data Access Broker (DAB)** with the result that DEIMS is fit to be harvested by GEO DAB. Consequently, any information about, and from, LTER sites form part of the GEO System of Systems.

In the coming decade, eLTER will explore options to collaborate in the ILTER context in capacity building in countries that are not yet participating in concerted long-term ecosystem research. This represents one of the focal areas in cooperating with the **UNESCO World Network of Biosphere Reserves (WNBR)**. Moreover, cooperation at sites, which are both LTER facilities and Biosphere Reserves, will be strengthened. A special emphasis will be on developing countries and on ways to improve the potential for performing standard measurements on ecosystem change and its drivers in accordance with GEO/GEOBON concepts (e.g. the integrated application of Essential Biodiversity Variables and Ecosystem Integrity concepts for identifying standard biotic and abiotic observation parameters, which forms the basis for determining the eLTER RI standard observation parameters. WNBR recommends Biosphere Reserves with a strong research focus to register their sites in DEIMS, and also use DEIMS to document the wealth of long-term data of these Biosphere Reserves.

A joint strategic position paper describes linkages specifically between the LTSER component of LTER in Europe and European Biosphere Reserves (EuroMAB). Further global links of eLTER RI (partly via ILTER) comprise the International Nitrogen Initiative, Global Land Project, FutureEarth, SAEON in South Africa, US-LTER, TERN in Australia, DataONE, the global CZO community and the CZ network in China.

4 Conclusions and recommendations

4.1 Conclusions

In its own design, eLTER RI will capitalise on 20-years of LTER-Europe experience in RI implementation and operation in most European countries, and utilise the most recent best examples at the national level, where national RI platforms have been developed in order to achieve concerted interactions with the European scale RIs. In connection to that, the eLTER RI is involved in strategic processes and projects in Europe (ESFRI, ESFRI 2030 Roadmap, ENVRI/ERIS) and anchored in global developments like GERI (Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure initiative) where eLTER has been one of the main initiators.

Several in depth analysis have been done on the role of eLTER with respect to its peers, and recommendations given how to improve eLTER's position, synergies and how streamlining the national activities can improve the sustainability. In 2019 eLTER's role in the European RI landscape was specified in consensus with eLTER's major peer RIs in a proximity analysis, highlighting the priority peers covered in chapter 3.3. Despite all pandemic induced constraints for networking and international collaborations activities since spring 2020, when eLTER PPP started, we progressed in developing collaboration with priority peers like ICOS.

4.2 Recommendations

- Global priority strategic partnerships for eLTER are the co-founders of GERI Continue to offer tangible support to the national eLTER processes from the PPP.
- Priority strategic partnerships identified in the stakeholder analysis for "Peers" -group during the next five years in Europe are:
 - Environmental Research Infrastructures (ESFRI): Lifewatch, ICOS, and AnaEE (if possible, establish MoUs)
 - Monitoring and observation networks and organizations in-situ and remote: UNECE WGE ICPs.
- Make all efforts to establish the eLTER ERIC despite the pandemic in accordance to the original time plan to anchor the eLTER RI through formal partnerships in the European and global landscape
- Enhance and strengthen the approach where the identified key responsables ("key accounts") (Barov et al. 2021) for each peer group can develop and maintain their contacts and inform other eLTER community about the developments
- Continue collaboration in ENVRI cluster and participate in the BeeRI work. eLTER will be an active participant in the cluster projects.
 - Co-location and interoperability developments are particularly enhanced with the targeted RI partners in the expected joint Horizon Europe project ENRISK
- Co-develop services with the other peer RIs in Europe and take advantage of their services

- Prominent element of such efforts: Sustain the DEIMS to become and hold the global source of site metadata and in the future to host data also from global sources.
- Strengthen and exemplify linkages to remote sensing communities.

5 References

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